

Direct Imaging and Location of Pb²⁺ and K⁺ in EMT Framework Type Zeolite

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ABSTRACT: The understanding of the structural framework and metal locations within zeolites are two critical aspects in order to tune and further exploit their properties as heterogeneous catalysts, advanced optical devices or as water remediation materials. The development of electron microscopy has made it possible to observe directly, the zeolitic framework and the distribution of extra-framework cations within the pores at the atomic level. Here, we have studied the EMT framework providing data with unprecedented spatial resolution, which have allowed the analysis of the FAU domains present in the framework. Additionally, the potassium and lead, (introduced by aqueous ion exchange) which were non-periodically distributed in the pores have been located. An alternative image mode, annular bright field, has been used proving its usefulness to extend the spatial resolution and increase the sensitivity towards light elements such as bridging oxygen. Finally, the combination of atomic imaging (local information) with the three- dimension electron diffraction tomography analysis (averaged information) allowed determining the Lead-EMT crystal symmetry to be *P6₃mc*.

1. INTRODUCTION

Zeolites are microporous materials with tunable porosity widely used as ion exchangers or heterogeneous catalysts¹ among many others applications. They are able to confine elements within their pores and they also exhibit very good thermal stability²⁻⁴. Due to the confinement capability that zeolites exhibit, they can protect extra-framework species, minimizing their agglomeration and release back to the environment as well as tuning their physical properties (work function or luminescence for example)⁵⁻¹⁸.

There are currently up to 253 different zeolite topologies¹⁹ in the International Zeolite Association (IZA) structure database; among them, TSC, EMT and FAU exhibit the lowest framework densities of 13.2~13.3 T/1000 Å³ of the aluminosilicate family. Lower density zeolites are highly desirable for soil treatment applications²⁰ or catalysis²¹. EMT was firstly synthesized in 1971²² as a mixture between FAU and EMT. The pure EMT framework, named EMC-2 after Elf (or Ecole Supérieure) Mulhouse Chimie - two, was obtained by Delprato and co-workers²³ in 1990 and the structure was completely solved by Baerlocher *et al.* four years later²⁴. EMT is the hexagonal polytype of the FAU-type zeolite (cubic) sharing the same layer units composed of sodalite cages (*t-toc*) linked by double 6-membered rings (*d6R*, *t-hpr*). The EMT framework contains large *t-wof* and *t-wou* cages with three and five 12-membered ring (12MR) windows respectively. In contrast with the zigzag channels of FAU and the 8-membered ring windows of TSC, EMT has straight access along three directions, all with 12MR windows. EMT has previously been used in biomedicine²⁵ and gas capture and separation²⁶. It also shows great potential for industrial applications such as petroleum cracking due to its large channel and cavity size.

Besides the use of zeolites as heterogeneous catalysts and water softeners, the capability of zeolites to capture different elements within their pore system is also attractive for various applications such optoelectronics or water remediation. The interest of occluding lead within the pores of zeolites or metal organic frameworks (MOFs) has re-gained much interest due to the possibility of tuning the optical response of lead-loaded zeolites while preventing lead discharge into the environment due to its coordination to the framework. The incorporation of lead species can be summarized in three families: (i) Unitary: Clusters (including single atom) with only one element^{14, 27}; (ii) Binary: Species formed by two elements, such as PbS, PbI₂, located inside the zeolite frameworks²⁸⁻³¹; (iii) Ternary: Lead compounds formed by three elements, CsPbI₃ and CsPbBr₃³².

To gain structural information, there are several characterization methods available to help explain the physico-chemical properties of zeolites. Such properties are strongly affected by the type of metal introduced, its size and location; therefore, characterization at atomic level is becoming indispensable to tailor the properties of materials at the nanoscale. Zeolite frameworks present high degree of symmetry, whereas the exchanged forms are usually disordered. Therefore, long-range techniques such as X-ray diffraction and Rietveld analysis do not always give the short-range information needed. In this sense, transmission electron microscopy is perhaps, the most powerful methodology as it can provide direct visualization of the framework and the guest species at an atomic level together with crystallographic and chemical information³³⁻³⁷. All these results have been achieved with thorough control of the electron dose, as zeolites are strongly beam sensitive. Working in probe mode offers a quick scan, reducing the sample damage. The possibility of obtaining sub-Ångstrom

probes together with the use of several detectors simultaneously allows for the collection of signals at high angle (annular dark field, ADF) providing information regarding the heavy elements. Meanwhile, an angular bright field detector (ABF) enhances the signal of light compounds³⁸⁻³⁹, which are scattered at low angle. Therefore, by combining the information from both detectors, determining the location and element type of both light and heavy elements is achievable.

In this work, EMT framework type zeolite was ion exchanged with $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ to finally obtain a partially loaded Pb-EMT. The characterization has been primarily carried out by Atomic-resolution transmission electron microscopy imaging that has been acquired by combining ADF and ABF detectors to obtain atomically resolved data of the framework and on the extraframework cations. These observations have been correlated with the data obtained by electron diffraction tomography. The existence of FAU intergrowths have been also analyzed based on this technique.

2. METHODS

2.1 Synthetic procedures. Pb-EMT: EMT was synthesized using previously reported method^{23, 40}. 1.45 g of sodium aluminate and 1.21 g of 50% NaOH solution was added to 7.8 g of deionized water, together with 1.76 g of 18-crown-6 and stirred vigorously. Once homogeneous 15.4 g silica solution (LUDOX AM-30) was added with stirring and left for 24 days at room temperature to incubate. The mixture was placed in a 45 mL Parr pressure vessel and heated for 12 days at 110°C. The product was filtered and washed with copious amounts of deionized water, then calcined in air at 540°C for 16 hours.

A potassium ion-exchange was performed by adding 4 g of EMT to 500 mL of 0.1 M KNO_3 solution and stirred overnight. The powder was recovered and washed with 1 L of distilled water and air-dried overnight. The exchange procedure was repeated a further two times.

The lead ion-exchange was carried out as follows, 2 g of EMT was added to 500 mL of 0.1 M $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution and stirred overnight. The powder was recovered and washed with 1 L of distilled water and air-dried overnight. The exchange and washing procedures were repeated a further two times.

2.2 Characterization. Scanning Electron Microscopy: STEM analyses were carried out in a JEOL Grand ARM 300, equipped with a cold Field Emission Gun (cold FEG) and operated at 300 kV. The column was fitted with a JEOL double aberration corrector, which was aligned prior the analyses to assure a maximum spatial resolution of 0.7 Å in scanning mode. The microscope was also equipped with a JEOL EDS and a Gatan Quantum Energy Filter for spectroscopic measurements. The main paragraph text follows directly on here.

3D-EDT: The 3D-EDT data was collected using JEOL.Shell software in a JEOL JEM2100 Plus electron microscope operated at 200 kV in transmission electron microscope (TEM) mode. A total collecting angle of 120 degrees was obtained by tilting the sample holder from -60°

to +60°. The intensities were extracted with EDT.Process software. Finally, the structure was solved with Sir2014⁴¹.

Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS): EDS data was collected using a JEOL JEM2100 Plus operated in STEM mode with an accelerating voltage of 200 kV.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM): The Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) images were collected in a JEOL JEM7800 Prime with a work distance of 7 mm under a landing voltage of 1 kV.

STEM simulation: The simulated ADF-STEM and ABF-STEM images along [100] were obtained with software QSTEM⁴². A supercell of $150 \times 150 \times 150 \text{ \AA}^3$ was constructed for a pure silica EMT. The probe array was 600×600 pixels with 0.032 Å resolution with the slice thickness of 1 Å. The detector geometries inner and outer angles were 50-200 mrad for ADF and 5-40 mrad for ABF.

Image treatment: In order to minimize the beam damage, the electron dose was significantly reduced in comparison with standard STEM conditions. For the current experiments, the total time for image acquisition ranged from 6 to 10 seconds, 1024×1024 pixels using an electron dose of $1120 \text{ e}^-/\text{\AA}^2$ to $2800 \text{ e}^-/\text{\AA}^2$. Under these conditions, images could be directly interpreted and all intensity analyses were performed over raw data. However, for a clearer visualization of the frameworks and of the light cations Random Noise 2D difference filter was used⁴³ from HREM Research Inc.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The EMT framework type is a zeolite with hexagonal symmetry and $P6_3/mmc$ space group. The lattice constants previously reported are $a = b = 17.215 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 28.082 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = 90^\circ$ and $\gamma = 120^\circ$. The morphology of the EMT particles was in agreement with the hexagonal symmetry presenting well-defined hexagonal particles with a thickness up to 500 nm and widths that reached up to several microns, see Figure 1.

This framework is formed by double six rings (d6Rs) and sodalite (*sod*) cages that when connected, forming *faujasite* layers (layer unit), with 12-membered rings formed along the *b* and *c* directions. The stacking sequence of these layers allow the formation of either EMT or FAU. By AA' stacking of *faujasite* sheets, EMT is obtained, where the adjacent two layers are related to each other through a mirror plane. Alternatively, in FAU, the stacking sequence is ABC, with each *faujasite* layer rotated 60° with respect to the previous one, and each *sod* cage related to its partner by an inversion centre.

For EMT, along the *b* axis, the 12MRs run parallel to the observation axis while the layer unit run perpendicular along the *c* axis in an AA'A stacking. The chemical formula for calcined EMC-2 has been reported to be $[\text{Na}_{20}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6][\text{Si}_{76}\text{Al}_{20}\text{O}_{192}]$ -EMT, where the 20 Na^+ cations that compensate the presence of Al tetrahedra, sit in three crystallographic sites at X2: 0.5890, 0.1770, 0.0470; X3: 0.6667, 0.3333, 0.6270; X4: 0.3571, 0.1790, 0.3880 with 0.25, 0.32 and 0.33 site occupancy respectively, see Figure S1. In Figure S1, the T (T=Si and Al) atoms are presented as blue,

brown, purple and green spheres corresponding to the different crystallographic sites, O in red, while X₂ appears in yellow, X₃ light blue and X₄ in pink being all of them associate to the 6SRs of the *sod* cages.

Analysis of FAU intergrowths. It has been previously mentioned that due to the structural similarities, (the use of the same building units differing only on how the layers stack) FAU and EMT can coexist in the same crystals^{23, 37-44}. Along [110] orientation, both hexagonal EMT and cubic FAU exhibit different manners of pillaring the *faujasite* layers; while for EMT there is a AA'AA'... stacking (Figure 2a) for FAU (Figure 2b) it follows ABC.. pillaring. These layers are formed by *sodalite* cages (*t-toc*), in pink, linked by d6Rs (*t-hpr*), purple, which are subsequently connected by also d6Rs (*t-hpr*) shown in green between different layers. An isolated *faujasite* layer is depicted in Figure 2c.

Because of these structural similarities, it could be expected that intergrowths of both phases due to the layer stacking sequence in a defective way would exist. In fact, there are many cases where EMT has been crystallized with the presence of FAU⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷. For EMT A and A' layers are mirror related to each other⁴⁸. While in FAU, layer B is shifted (1/2a, 1/2b, 1/2c) relative to layer A and layer C is shifted (1/2a, 0, 1/2c) relative to layer A. The origin of the A, B, C layers are marked in the Figure 2d. Large *t-wou* and *t-wof* cages for EMT and *t-fau* cages for FAU are formed between layers. *t-wof*, *t-wou* and *t-fau* have 3, 5 and 4 12MRs windows respectively.

Figure 2e corresponds to the C_s-corrected STEM ADF image of an EMT crystal with structural defects in the framework evidenced by the diffuse spots (yellow arrows) in the Fourier diffractogram, Figure 2e inset. This region, of approximately 6 nm along [110]/[100]_{EMT} zone axis, corresponds to a FAU domain, enclosed by EMT regions. In another crystal, the sequence AA'ABB'A'AA' can be observed, Figure 2f. This region is formed by two FAU domains connected through a mirror plane (defined by BB' layers) enclosed within the EMT. For direct interpretation, the schematic model has been superimposed displayed in different colors to distinguish the three zones as shown in Figure 2f. The left (green) and right (yellow/red) regions, corresponding to the EMT framework, allow the clear visualization of the 12 MRs, marked by blue dashed circles. While in between, the twin plane is marked in pink color. By observing this structure along the [001] projection, Figure 2g, these two EMT domains would overlap, where the 12 MRs marked with a blue background, would be blocked by *sodalite* cages from the twin plane, BB', shown in Figure 2f. The large 12MR windows of the BB' stacking would be also blocked by the EMT *sodalite* cages from both sides as shown in Figure 2g. By observing figure 2f, yellow circles, it can be appreciated the existence of a faint signal inside the 12MRs in the twin plane that is associated with the presence of *sodalite* cages from the EMT region, partially blocking these channels. These 12MRs are fully empty in the EMT area (blue dashed circles).

Analysis of EMT framework and extraframework cations. It is possible to synthesize the EMT framework with different Si/Al ratios, but in general terms, the most common zeolite obtained has been EMC-2 with a chemical

formula [Na₂₀(H₂O)₆] [Si₇₆Al₂₀O₁₉₂]²³⁻²⁴. In this work, Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analyses were used to estimate the chemical composition of the current EMT. The results obtained were reasonable and in agreement with the data reported. The most relevant differences with previous works were that K⁺ was also used as counter ion together with Na⁺, and that Pb²⁺ was also detected due to the ion-exchange. Based on these results, the electro-neutrality would be maintained as the sum of the positive charges from the cationic species would be 18 that would compensate the 20 (AlO₄⁻) of the framework. The small mismatch between the cations and aluminum is related to a slight experimental error of the technique or to the presence of protonic species H⁺ from the water. In fact, the excess of O detected could be associated to water adsorbed in the pores. For simplicity, hereafter, we will refer only K⁺ when considering both Na⁺ and K⁺ as due to their low content and similar atomic number it is not possible to distinguish between both metals.

Annular Dark Field (ADF) together with Annular Bright Field (ABF) imaging modes can reveal unique information especially at local level. By using an ADF detector, the electrons scattered at high angle are used to form the images allowing the visualization of heavier elements as the signal is proportional to Z^{1.6-2.49-50}, where Z is the atomic number. On the other hand, ABF provides complementary information of the framework, as it is more sensitive to light compounds, even with higher spatial resolution^{36, 38-39}.

For the EMT framework type, the most suitable projections for the structural observation are [110]/[100] two equivalent orientations with the minimum atomic column overlapping; hereafter, we will refer only to [100] for simplicity. Figure 3a corresponds to the C_s-corrected STEM-ABF micrograph of Pb loaded EMT zeolite along [100] orientation; in this case, the atomic columns appear as black dots and the big pores which are clearly observable correspond to the 12MRs. The white arrows point to a structural defect resulting for the merge of two *faujasite* sheets which breaks the AA'A stacking, the FD, shown inset, proves that the spatial resolution that can be achieved is at least 1.2 Å represented by the 00024 diffraction spot, marked by a yellow circle. The symmetry-averaged image is depicted in figure 3b; although the ABF data already presents sufficient degree of quality to analyze the structure at atomic level, the averaged data is displayed to facilitate the observation of some particular aspects. Symmetry averaging image treatment presents certain advantages as it allows discussion about plane symmetry elements and it significantly increases the signal-to-noise ratio. On the other hand, it introduces undesired periodicity, which is disadvantageous for non-periodic materials such as zeolites with uneven cationic distribution. Here, symmetry averaging has been used to improve the signal-to-noise ratio; for EMT topology the reported space group is *P6₃/mmc* (194); therefore, its plane group along the [100] should be *p2gm*. The averaged data assuming this space group is depicted in figure 3b highlighting i) T atoms (blue arrow); ii) Oxygen bridges (red arrows) and additional signals that are not part of the framework (pink and yellow arrows). To facilitate the in-

terpretation, the model of the framework has been superimposed where the Si appears in blue and O in red, for clarity, the presence of extraframework cationic species has been omitted. Figure S2 compares the experimental data (Figure S2a) with the simulated image (Figure S2b) of the all-silica framework (without cationic species to highlight the differences between the bare framework and the experimental data) Figure S2b; in both cases, colored arrows have been used to point the framework atoms and the extraframework sites. Figure 3b exhibits excellent image quality and it corroborates the feasibility of ABF imaging for the observation of light compounds as oxygen bridges. In addition, the two distinct signals that do not belong to the framework can be inferred to be cationic species; however, an aspect that need to be considered is that, to obtain this image, symmetry restraints have been introduced and the presence of those extraframework species do not necessarily need to be periodic. In order to evaluate this aspect and to study the possible introduction of Pb²⁺ in the pores after ion exchange, we turned into C_s-corrected STEM-ADF without imposing any symmetry averaging, Figure 4. Figure 4a depicts the correspondent C_s-corrected STEM-ADF data of the Pb-EMT zeolite on the [100] projection, in here, the contrast is reversed respect to the ABF data where the atomic columns appearing as bright spots and in which the 12 MRs are observed together with the d6Rs and the *sodalite* cages. Interestingly, a strong contrast is observed as bright spots, which appear at specific sites in a non-periodic manner. The areas marked by rectangles with different colors, numbered 1 to 3, were enlarged to analyze the contrast variations at different regions of the crystal, while the additional dashed yellow rectangle corresponds to the area that is magnified in Figure 4b. The intensity profiles along several *sodalite* cages were extracted (Figure S3) observing some maxima corresponding to those bright spots. In Figure 4a, the 12 MRs are clearly visualized as empty pores; meanwhile the bright spots would be placed at those sites where Na⁺ have been proposed to occupy, corresponding to the X₃ and X₄ sites. This observation is in agreement with the data obtained with an ABF detector (see Figure 3b yellow arrow) that indicates a very strong signal (that appears periodically due to the symmetry averaged introduced) near the oxygen bridges. Such signal observed in the ABF and in the ADF cannot derive from the O bridges, due to their low scattering factor, and therefore it is owed to the presence of single Pb²⁺ sites, single atoms or atomic columns. Due to the low initial occupancy of the extraframework cations (K⁺ and Na⁺ here), it cannot be estimated whether Pb²⁺ is in the form of single atoms or if there are several Pb²⁺ on the same column. Nevertheless, X₃ and X₄ sites correspond to two distinct atomic sites with different coordinates; however, due to their proximity in the projected image ≈ 0.5 Å it cannot be initially distinguished whether Pb²⁺ replaced X₃, X₄ or both.

To deeply investigate the ion-exchange capability and therefore the location of the cations, Figure S4a shows the schematic model of a *sodalite* cage with the same color code as Figure S1 a color code that displays T₃ (T=Si, Al) crystallographic sites in purple, forming an s6R, where the light blue sphere corresponds to the cationic site at X₃.

Blue T atoms correspond to T₁; brown spheres are the T₂ sites, purple T₃ and in green ones the T₄. Cations at X₄ are marked in pink, while cationic sites at X₂ appears in yellow. If Pb²⁺ would occupy X₄ site, this would correspond to the location of Pb²⁺ on top of the S6Rs of the *t-toc* cage, see figure S4a. On the other hand, if Pb²⁺ would replace X₃ this one would be in a similar position, on top of another S6Rs of the *t-toc* cage, but closer to the framework. Figure S4b presents an entire unit cell with the same color code showing, along this projection, the proximity between X₃ and X₄. It is important to mention that no experimental evidence was found of Pb²⁺ occupying the X₂ sites, that in the projected image would be inside the s6Rs very close to T₁ atoms.

The other extraframework signal that was detected in the experimental data that did not belong to the zeolitic framework was observed within the s6Rs but not as intense as the aforementioned one associated to Pb²⁺. In this case, the signal marked by a pink arrow in the ABF data, figure 3b, and by a pink dashed circle in figure 4b, would correspond to K⁺ cations (based on the chemical analyses the K⁺ content is much higher in comparison with Na⁺, although because of their similar atomic number it would not be possible to distinguish between them). These extraframework species were not periodically distributed along the entire framework, as empty s6Rs could also be identified, see dashed blue circles in Figure 4b. This observation could be associated to the presence of aluminum in the framework suggesting that the aluminum was not periodically distributed as the empty s6Rs would be linked to the absence of Al at those sites; meanwhile the extraframework cationic presence suggest the existence of Al around them. Figure 4c depicts an enlarged image of a 12 MR, obtained from the yellow dashed rectangle in figure 4b, where the K⁺ can be identified within the s6R. Two different intensity profiles were plotted along the arrows 1 and 2, figure 4d, where two peaks are present, the first one and more intense, corresponds to an atomic column of the framework, Si or Si+Al; while the other belongs to the K⁺. The measured projected distances were d₁ = 2.05 Å corresponding to the distance between T₂-cation and d₂ = 2.28 Å corresponding to the distance between the T₄-cation, these measurements (slightly shorter) are in agreement with the data reported for Na-EMT (for X₄ sites), where projected distances are 2.20 Å and 2.42 Å, respectively. Furthermore, no evidences of K⁺ or Pb²⁺ present at X₂ sites were found in any of the equivalent sites.

Based on these observations, Pb²⁺ would preferentially replace the cations at the X₃ sites, figure 4b yellow arrows. Despite that X₃ and X₄ sites are too close to be distinguished, we have not observed evidences of the presence of Pb²⁺ at the s6Rs denoted by pink dashed circles in figure 4b; that would correspond to K⁺ at X₄ sites. Therefore, as the K⁺ at X₄ sites have two equivalent positions if Pb²⁺ would enter at X₄; this stronger signal would be observed at the sites indicated by a pink circle and at the sites pointed by yellow arrows. As this is not the case, it is possible to conclude that Pb²⁺ would only go into the sites denoted as X₃; in fact, as K⁺ is at X₄ the total signal detected at X₃ would be mostly owed to Pb²⁺ but with a contribution

from K^+ situated at X4. Despite that, the Pb^{2+} signal was not homogeneously observed along the entire crystal, it always occupied a particular crystallographic site; however, due to the low occupancy of the extraframework cations, 0.33 for X4, it does not appear along the entire crystal. From these observations, it can be also inferred that Pb^{2+} would compensate the electric charge of the cations at X2 sites; as from the experimental data no signal was detected at these positions suggesting that the cations were removed from these sites but Pb^{2+} did not fill the positions; the electro-neutrality was maintained as one Pb^{2+} would compensate two monoatomic species of either Na^+ or K^+ . For comparison, simulated data were compared with the experimental data, see Figure S5. Figure S5a corresponds to the simulated image of the EMT framework with no cations added to the structure, Figure S5b displays the same image with different amounts of K^+ and Pb^{2+} added to the system. The blue dashed circle corresponds to a s6R where the K^+ are not observed, the amount of K^+ which was placed at that site was 6 atoms in that column; therefore, for a given thickness of 8 nm (≈ 4 unit cells) 6 atoms of K^+ per column were not detectable. The pink dashed circle corresponds to the K^+ at the s6Rs (18 atoms per column, which are clearly visible). Meanwhile, the yellow arrow points at the signal owed to the Pb^{2+} (in this case the column was filled by 6 atoms). Figure S5c corresponds to the experimental data obtained. **To discard that the strong signal observed can be the result of the possible interaction of the framework atoms with the cations (due to their proximity on the projection image) additional simulations with different cationic content are depicted in Figures S5d and S5e.**

Framework analysis and crystallographic determination of Pb^{2+} , K^+ position. It has been proved so far, how image analysis at the atomic level can provide local information of the zeolitic framework and extraframework cations. On the other hand, electron diffraction can deliver more general information as the solution obtained is based on an average over several unit cells. The structure of Pb-EMT zeolite was solved based on the diffraction intensities extracted from the 3D-EDT using direct methods. Figure S6 displays the extracted electron diffraction patterns along the main crystallographic orientations Figures S6a, S6b and S6c belongs to the c^* , b^* and a^* projections respectively. Along c^* axis, this zeolite exhibits 6-fold symmetry, while two perpendicular mirror planes are present along the other orientations, running along a^* , b^* and c^* axes, see Figures S6b and S6c. From the $h k l$ plane (Figure S6d) the reflection condition $o o l: l=2n$ was confirmed, marked by a blue rectangle. For $h k o$, $h k l$, $h k 2$, $h k 3$ planes, $h h l$ and $h-h l$ ($l = 1, 2, 3, 4$) reflections are marked with green and pink rectangles respectively. Reflections $h-h l$ appear in all the four layers while $h h l$ only appear when $l = 2n$ (Figures S6e-h). These reflection conditions are in agreement with the extinction symbol $P_{-} c$. Thus, only three space groups fulfill these conditions $P6_3 m c$ (186), $P-62 c$ (190), $P6_3 / m m c$ (194). The three of them were used to solve the structure obtaining reliable results when $P6_3 m c$ and $P6_3 / m m c$ were used. **The structure solution assuming the highest symmetry would be to $P6_3 / m m c$ (194) in agreement with the EMT topology²⁴, Figure 5a. Based on the data extracted from 3D-**

EDT, see table S2 for atomic coordinates, Pb^{2+} cations would occupy the $t-wof$ cage with 4 equivalent sites, represented as green spheres in Figure 5a. Meanwhile, the light cations Na^+/K^+ situated within the large $t-wou$ cages has 12 equivalent sites per cell, rose spheres. These results are in concordance with the experimental atomic resolution data presented in figures 3 and 4 along the [100] projection (yellow arrows of Figures 3 and 4). Although the averaged solution from 3D-EDT suggested four equivalent positions, the experimental C_s -corrected data revealed that that Pb^{2+} did not occupy all the four sites. Instead, Pb^{2+} would not fill the sites situated opposite to each other corresponding to either Pb_A or Pb_B in Figure 5a. Based on these observations, if two Pb^{2+} atoms from either Pb_A or Pb_B sites are removed, the space group would lower its symmetry changing from $P6_3 / m m c$ to $P6_3 m c$, see Figure 5b where the two Pb^{2+} atoms (green spheres) are marked by yellow circles. On the other hand, light cations Na^+/K^+ were found at the s6Rs of the $t-wou$ cages (rose spheres). At this crystallographic site, some of the Na^+/K^+ symmetric equivalent sites overlap with the Pb^{2+} along [110]/[100] projections as shown in Figure 5b, but they are in different cages.

To reach out this findings, we turned out to image analyses, Figure 5c. Figure 5c displays the ADF symmetry averaged data obtained after using the plane groups marked in the Figure 5c; p_1 is the experimental data with no symmetry operation imposed, only translation. The other two images were obtained after using pg (plane group from $P6_3 m c$) and $p2gm$ (plane group from $P6_3 / m m c$). To clearly highlight the differences between the three images, color circles were superimposed in the figure, green would correspond to the strong signals associated to the Pb^{2+} , rose circle indicates the light signals from the K^+ and the yellow circle indicates equivalent sites for Pb^{2+} , which is actually the difference between the data analyzed. While the Pb^{2+} and K^+ , green and rose circles respectively, are equal for the three cases; the major difference is indicated by the yellow circle as a strong signal is observed for $p2gm$ that is absent for pg and for p_1 (experimental data). Based on this significant difference, it is possible to conclude that Pb^{2+} did not fill the sites situated opposite to each other and that the correct plane group should be pg and therefore the correct space group considering this cationic distribution is $P6_3 m c$.

By comparing the experimental data acquired by C_s -corrected imaging at atomic level it was possible to elucidate preferential sites for Pb^{2+} and for K^+ evaluating also the ion exchange capability and which sites are more suitable to be initially exchanged. The electron diffraction data allowed the characterization over an averaged volume of the structure obtaining results, which were in agreement with the observations by C_s -corrected STEM, allowing us to conclude that Pb^{2+} locates in the $t-wof$ cage and K^+ locates in the $t-wou$ cage. The most significant difference between the images and the diffraction data was that images showed preferential sites for Pb^{2+} and K^+ , **and that by imaging it was possible to acquired local information observing the absence of cations at positions that based on the electron diffraction should be occupied. This is because the results obtained by electron diffraction were averaged**

over a relatively large area (100 nm, limited by the diffraction aperture used). Therefore, the atomic coordinates occupied by Pb^{2+} and Na^+/K^+ , which were not part of the zeolite framework were the result of no single atoms but the preferential sites for cationic occupancy that in average tend to go to those sites. These results illustrate the importance of combining electron diffraction with atomic resolution imaging to achieve a complete characterization of the structure of zeolites especially with the intention of gaining information at local level.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, a combination of various electron microscopy techniques has been used to analyze the structure and the ion exchange capability of EMT zeolite, where K^+ and Pb^{2+} were both introduced in the pores. By taking a multi-technique approach, the particular features of Pb-EMT have been revealed. SEM data allowed the morphology visualization obtaining symmetry elements, which facilitated the structural solution.

C_s -corrected STEM observations displayed data with enough quality to obtain atomic resolution information, even showing the oxygen bridges as well as cations Pb^{2+} and K^+ that were atomically distributed over the framework. The atomic coordinates were determined by 3D-EDT. Both the Pb^{2+} and K^+ were found to be outside the sodalite cages above the s6Rs of these cages. While Pb^{2+} was in the *t-wof* cages K^+ was in *t-wou* cages. Overall, atomic resolution images provided insights of the local structure of Pb-EMT gaining information on the ion exchange capability and on the location and periodicity of the extraframework cations, which helped to achieve a more accurate structural solution. The combination of 3D-EDT with the image analysis concluded that crystal symmetry had to be reduced from $P6_3/mmc$ to $P6_3mc$.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. "This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>."

Experimental details, including chemicals, synthesis and characterization techniques.

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Figure 1. a) Low magnification SEM image of several EMT particles. b) SEM image of an isolated EMT crystal with hexagonal plate morphology.

Figure 2. a) EMT model along $[110]/[100]_{EMT}$ orientation. b) FAU model along $[110]$. c) Schematic model of a layer unit (*faujasite* layer), front view. d) Top view of the model corresponding to a layer unit. The origins for the subsequent layers are marked by yellow, blue and green dots. Color code: Rose cages correspond to *t-toc* (sodalite cages); *t-hpr* (double 6-membered ring, D6R) appear in green (between layers) and in purple (within per layer) cages. e) C_s -corrected STEM-ADF micrograph recorded along the $[110]/[100]_{EMT}$ with a FAU intergrowth marked by yellow lines. The Fourier Diffractogram (FD) is shown inset with yellow arrows pointing at the diffuse streaks. f) Closer observation of another crystal where two FAU domains are joint by a mirror plane BB' . The dashed blue circles correspond to the $12MRs$, while the yellow ones denote the partial blocked $12MRs$ within the twin plane. g) Schematic representation of the structure model of f) along $[001]_{EMT}$ direction.

Figure 3. C_s -corrected STEM-ABF data of Pb-EMT. a) Atomic resolution data along [100] projection with the FD shown inset. The white arrow corresponds to a structural defect. The yellow circle in the FD indicates the maximum transfer information corresponding to the 00024 spot. b) Symmetry $p2gm$ averaged data with the framework model superimposed. The red arrows point at O bridges, the blue one corresponds to the T atoms, and the yellow and pink ones to extraframework signals.

Figure 4. a) C_s -corrected STEM-ADF along [100] of Pb-EMT. The three colored rectangles correspond to the areas where the intensity analysis was performed. The dashed yellow rectangle indicates where figure b) was obtained from. b) Closer observation of the framework where the bright spots are marked by yellow arrows. An empty s6R is denoted by a dashed blue circle. The dashed pink circle corresponds to a s6R with a cation inside. c) Enlarged image of a s6R where the two arrows indicate where the intensity profiles were extracted from, numbered as 1 and 2. d) Intensity profiles along 1 and 2.

Figure 5. a) Structural solution using $P6_3/mmc$ (194). b) Structural model after removing Pb_A or Pb_B leading into a lower symmetry $P6_3mc$. c) C_s -corrected STEM-ADF data after symmetry averaging. The colored circles indicate the same crystallographic sites in each image, green corresponds to Pb^{2+} , rose K^+ and yellow would be the equivalent site to the Pb^{2+} marked by a green circle.

TOC Graphic

